

Research data management and data sharing in Education Research

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Context

This study is part of the project entitled:

“LOS DATOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN ABIERTO EN CIENCIAS DE LA EDUCACION COMO MOTOR DEL CAMBIO SOCIAL”

(EDUCATIONAL SCIENCE RESEARCH DATA AS A DRIVER OF SOCIAL CHANGE)

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Y UNIVERSIDADES

Introduction

There is still a huge volume of digital data largely underused.

In the Education Sciences field the lack of established data sharing practices poses a barrier.

In Spain, while some progress has been made, challenges and barriers persist in this field.

Objective

To identify current practices in research data management by Spanish researchers and research groups in the field of Education.

Methods

- We have designed and implemented an anonymous and confidential survey.
 - To create it, we used LimeSurvey, an open-source application for conducting online questionnaires.
 - Then, it was submitted to validation by a mixed panel of experts.
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Methods

The survey is composed by 37 questions, divided into 3 blocks:

A. Personal data

B. Creation and re-use of data

C. Data preservation

It was designed with questions to gather information on researchers' beliefs and practices in data use and re-use, data maintenance and preservation, the influence of funding, and the role of journals in data sharing.

Methods

The survey was sended by email to researchers in the field of Education Sciences of Spanish universities.

The questionnaire was sent in June 2023 and closed in September 2023.

A total of 356 responses were received.

Results

1. Where researchers tend to publish according to the origin of journals

Results

2. Do the researchers consider important to share their research data?

A nearly 90% positive attitude towards data sharing was found.

→ Specifically, 48% of researchers consider sharing their data to be important and 42% indicate that currently do not share their data but express an interest in doing so in the future.

In contrast, a 10% of researchers do not share their data and show no intention of doing so.

Results

3. Who is responsible for managing data in the research in which the researchers are involved?

Results

4. ¿Have you developed a data management plan?

Of the total of researchers, 59% have never developed a DMP and a notable 13% did not know the question or did not respond.

Only a 28% of them have developed a DPM at least once.

Results

4. Data management tasks implemented by researchers

Results

5. The main reasons for developing data management actions

Results

5. The main reasons for developing data management actions

- *“Requirement established in the informed consent approved by the **ethics committee**”*
- *“We consider it necessary for **research ethics**”*
- *“Requirements of the journals where the results are published”*
- *“At the request of the journal in which the results associated with those data were published”*
- *“University's **ethical code**”*
- *“The university's **ethics committee** requires it”*
- *“Necessary for the approval of the project by the **Ethics Commitee** of our university”*

Conclusions

The findings of this study offer a glimpse into some challenges according to data management within the field of Education Sciences in Spain.

Consequently, it is essential to identify the barriers that may hinder effective data sharing and management in Education research delving into the specific particularities of the research of this field.

For this reason, it is important to design and offer training on data management as well as developing good practices guidelines having in mind the specific needs and interests of the professionals of this area.

Furthermore...

- We are working on a qualitative research in order to go deeper into the reasons and perceptions that the quantitative results have suggested us.

**Thank you very
much for your
attention!
¡Muchas gracias!
Vielen Dank!**

If you want to follow our work...

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